

Towards Offloading C/C++ Kernels and ONNX Models to CGRAs through MLIR

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Abstract. Efficient execution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) workloads in edge environments with constrained energy and compute resources is crucial due to the growing adoption of edge AI across various domains. Coarse Grained Reconfigurable Arrays (CGRAs) offer a balance between hardware specialization and flexibility, enabling instruction and data parallelism by spatially distributing computation while leveraging data locality through distributed memory. CGRAs have focused on optimizing inner loops of kernels written in programming languages like C, but since AI models are expressed in different formats, new compilation techniques are necessary to fully exploit the benefits offered by CGRAs for edge AI needs. In this paper, we present our Multi Level Intermediate Representation (MLIR) based approach to extract and compile workloads from either C/C++ or Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) models to a RISC-V based system with a CGRA acting as an accelerator. Data Flow Graph (DFG) representations of the extracted computations are used to generate CGRA configurations through conventional mapping, and an additional MLIR-based backend enables producing binaries where the RISC-V interfaces with the CGRA through custom instructions.

Keywords: RISC-V · CGRA · ONNX · Edge AI · MLIR

1 Introduction

The emergence of AI is driving the growth of new applications in a wide range of domains, with a large focus on edge use cases. New edge-oriented platforms such as NVIDIA’s Jetson series, Google’s Coral, or Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) based flows have gained prominence to support these applications. However, even more efficient execution of AI models is still necessary for greater scalability while reducing the increasing energy costs.

CGRAs are a type of well known but not widely adopted co-processor architecture, apt at accelerating computations expressed as DFGs. They provide

a compromise between dedicated hardware design, configurability, and the energy consumption of Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), versus which literature reviews support that CGRAs may achieve a superior performance–energy trade-off if properly exploited [15]. Offloading computations to CGRAs is often performed by targeting compute-intensive kernels written in C/C++. Some methods resort to re-writing code with specific APIs, while others to custom compilers at the LLVM-IR level. Since computations are not explicitly represented as graphs, which CGRA mappers require as inputs, these approaches must identify loop-carried dependencies, nested operations, and partition the computation. However, at this level, the loss of context and semantic information hinders the exploitation of acceleration potential. MLIR may address this by preserving high-level algorithmic and parallelism information, aiding partitioning through custom dialects and transformation passes, and enabling the support for heterogeneous targets.

Concurrently, execution of AI models is supported by widely-extended frameworks like Pytorch, TensorFlow, or ONNX through specific backends to run the models. ONNX is an open format to represent trained neural models (including the topology and weights) and is interoperable with other frameworks. It represents models as DFGs where each node is a high-level neural network operation such as convolutions or ReLU. Some approaches already exist to map ONNX to custom hardware, including CGRAs, but this is done by converting the models to Low Level Virtual Machine (LLVM) or MLIR, thus losing graph level information, which must then be reconstructed [20]. Even so, domain-specific operations, e.g., ReLU, may be completely lost as they are converted to subroutines using conventional instructions.

We explore MLIR to improve the offloading of both C/C++ and ONNX models to CGRAs for acceleration. MLIR is an open-source compiler framework for defining and optimizing multiple levels of abstraction, from high-level representations like TensorFlow to low-level hardware instructions. MLIR facilitates efficient transformations, optimizations, and code generation across diverse platforms. In this work, we target C/C++ by compiling to MLIR and using a custom dialect to extract DFGs for mapping, exploiting existing optimizations, and introducing explicit CGRA semantics. We target ONNX by implementing a ONNX to DFG conversion, leveraging the high-level information present in models directly. The subsequent mapping of the DFGs is converted to a second dialect for CGRA configuration, enabling the generation of final binaries for a RISC-V + CGRA system through a single process.

2 Related Work

2.1 CGRA Frameworks and Designs

ML-CGRA [11] is an MLIR-based compilation approach for CGRAs. The assumed CGRA model is loosely coupled, containing a local scratchpad memory and a DMA module for external memory access. The functional units of the CGRA are connected in a king mesh, and buffers between units support the

stalling of data transfers for a configurable number of cycles. The units contain common operations for AI workloads, like *multiply-and-accumulate* and *max*. Models from PyTorch, TensorFlow, or ONNX are lowered to MLIR, and passes such as operation fusion and loop tiling are implemented. Then, a pattern matching pass identifies sequences of operations for acceleration and converts them to custom `cgra-dialect`. For one benchmark AI model, the approach outperforms low-level mapping, which recovers DFG information from LLVM-IR by $3.15\times$ on a 4×4 CGRA. However, the original model information is still lost by conversion to MLIR and potentially only partially recovered. Furthermore, integration with a host processor is not addressed.

Morpher [20] is an open-source framework designed to explore and simulate CGRA designs by supporting Design Space Exploration (DSE) via an architecture description language. The flow relies on annotating loops in the source code, and then a custom LLVM pass is used to extract DFGs from these portions. The mapper performs spatial mapping and modulo scheduling, exploiting a generated memory bank layout generated during DFG extraction. The DFGs generation addresses challenges like control divergence, recurrence edges, and predication. Still, the approach is limited to arriving at a valid mapping and its' functional validation through simulation. Thus, the experimental evaluation focuses on comparisons with previous state-of-the-art mappers, where Morpher shows comparable results in shorter mapping times. However, the flow requires manual partitioning of code by annotating target kernels, by relying on LLVM-IR information it suffers from the mentioned issues regarding information loss, and does not address how the partitioned code links back to the original application.

SO(DA)² (Software-Defined Architectures for Data Analytics) [19] introduces the *soda* dialect, which is used to partition input applications in LLVM-IR format, originating from C/C++ through Clang, or AI models converted to MLIR. The target CGRA is OpenCGRA [17], a generator supporting a generic model with a configurable interconnection between functional units, and between units and one or more scratchpad banks. Operations like loop flattening and unrolling are applied to the intermediate representations, followed by DFG generation and mapping. Performance metrics are then evaluated, the design parameters tuned, and the process is repeated until target criteria are met. The mapper is a greedy process stopping at the first valid mapping for the lowest possible initiation interval. Through simulation via OpenCGRA, the optimal initiation interval is achieved for 10 DFGs, but as the focus is on DSE capabilities and CGRA mapping strategies, no absolute performance metrics are presented, nor details on the specifics of the dialect and orchestration with the host code.

2.2 ONNX Transformation Tools

This section overviews tools for transforming ONNX models. Each tool addresses distinct aspects of model handling, from model execution in JavaScript environments to low-level representation and model serialization, contributing important functionalities to ONNX model manipulation.

`onnx-mlir` [9] is an LLVM-based project that aims to lower ONNX models into MLIR [8]. MLIR is an extensible compiler infrastructure that enables sophisticated optimization and hardware-targeted transformations, making `onnx-mlir` an important tool for performance-sensitive applications. By translating ONNX operations to MLIR dialects, `onnx-mlir` enables advanced optimizations through compiler passes and facilitates deployment on specialized hardware accelerators, such as GPU and FPGAs. The lowering process in `onnx-mlir` decomposes complex ONNX operations into intermediate representations at the cost of losing the explicit graph structure and input data sizes. While some state-of-the-art approaches recover this information using LLVM-IR analysis, such as Morpher [20], our approach aims to preserve it by converting ONNX graphs into DFGs suitable for CGRA mapping. This strategy also provides better visualization possibilities, which facilitates the debugging process.

`onnxruntime-web`⁴ is a JavaScript library that extends the ONNX Runtime framework to enable ONNX model inference directly within web browsers. Leveraging WebAssembly (Wasm) and WebGL technologies for acceleration provides a lightweight and efficient environment for running machine-learning models without needing a backend server. This client-side execution capability facilitates rapid prototyping and deploying interactive machine-learning applications in web-based interfaces. While `onnxruntime-web` focuses on inference rather than model transformation, it demonstrates that ONNX models can target non-native contexts, highlighting the flexibility of the format and motivating the exploration of its use for contexts such as front-end for CGRA mapping.

`onnx2json`⁵ is a Python library that converts ONNX models into a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) structure. By serializing the model’s structure, the conversion provides a means to manipulate the graph at a high level. The JSON format captures essential details such as nodes, edges, input and output specifications, and model metadata, enabling visualization and easier interfacing with other systems. We re-implement this parsing step in the approach proposed in this paper, extending its capability to retrieve information from the originating ONNX files.

3 Compiling to RISC-V + CGRA System through MLIR

We consider as our compilation target a RISC-V based System-on-Chip (SoC) where a CGRA instance is used as the accelerator for AI workloads. The vast majority of CGRA implementations rely on generating configuration words via external tools, which are then held in a local context memory of the CGRA [3]. This may impose significant resource requirements as a function of the dimensions of CGRAs and the mapped DFGs. Furthermore, use of the CGRA by a host processor is implemented through design-specific APIs or direct access to memory mapped CGRA registers [16, 5, 21, 10], hindering adoption of these accelerators due to the required source modifications.

⁴ <https://www.npmjs.com/package/onnxruntime-web>

⁵ <https://github.com/PINTO0309/onnx2json>

Fig. 1. Proposed flow show paths for conversion of C/C++ code (through MLIR) and ONNX models (through graph transformations) into CGRA configurations, and linking into RISC-V binary through MLIR ecosystem

Instead, we propose integrating the generation of CGRA configurations into a unified compilation flow, as shown in Figure 1. We explore two paths to arrive at mappable DFGs through MLIR, with the motivation that this ecosystem can provide our intended integrated compilation flow where a singular binary is produced for a RISC-V core containing the required CGRA control.

One path accepts C/C++ code and is further explained in Section 3.1, while the second targets ONNX models as inputs, as explained in Section 3.2. In short, the C/C++ path uses the Polygeist [13] framework to generate MLIR code, and a custom dialect is then employed for DFG extraction. The second accepts models in ONNX format, i.e., graphs where each node represents very high-level operations, such as convolutions over tensors of arbitrary size, which we convert to DFGs exposing the underlying operations.

Both paths are intended to generate the same DFG format, which is suitable to be used as an input to state-of-the-art CGRA mappers [2, 7, 18]. We propose to convert the resulting mapping information (e.g., operation assignments to functional units, configuration time steps, *etc.*) into statements of an additional custom dialect that expresses these configuration steps. This dialect will be implemented by a respective custom RISC-V extension.

To link with the remaining code which was not offloaded, and should now call or interface with the CGRA, the partitioned segments in the C/C++ path are replaced with the configuration dialect, and to invoke an offloaded ONNX model, methods already exist to call ONNX models from C code which do not require knowledge of underlying hardware details, such as the *ONNX Runtime for C* [14], or even baremetal methods such as *TensorFlow Lite for Microcontrollers (TFLM)* [6]. Thus, the offloaded computation can be merged with the remaining application, which is expressed in conventional dialects, to produce

```

func.func @mac(%arg0: memref<?xi32>, %arg1: memref<?xi32>) -> i32 {
  %c0_i32 = arith.constant 0 : i32
  %0 = affine.for %arg2 = 0 to 100 iter_args(%arg3 = %c0_i32) -> (i32) {
    %1 = affine.load %arg0[%arg2] : memref<?xi32>
    %2 = affine.load %arg1[%arg2] : memref<?xi32>
    %3 = arith.muli %1, %2 : i32
    %4 = arith.addi %arg3, %3 : i32
    affine.yield %4 : i32
  }
  return %0 : i32
}

```

(a) MLIR code generated by Polygeist for a C/C++ multiply and accumulate kernel

```

func.func @mac(%arg0: memref<?xi32>, %arg1: memref<?xi32>) -> i32 attributes {llvm.linkage =
↪ #llvm.linkage<external>} {
  %c0 = arith.constant 0 : index
  %c0_i32 = arith.constant 0 : i32
  "cgra.deploy" {
    %0 = vector.transfer_read %arg0[%c0], %c0_i32 : memref<100xi32>, vector<100xi32>
    %1 = vector.transfer_read %arg1[%c0], %c0_i32 : memref<100xi32>, vector<100xi32>
    %2 = arith.muli %0, %1 : vector<100xi32>
    %3 = vector.reduction <add>, %2 : vector<100xi32> into i32
  }
  return %3 : i32
}

```

(b) code kernel transformed and identified with the partitioning dialect

Fig. 2. Example identification of candidate code for CGRA from C/C++ input

a single binary into which the CGRA configuration process is embedded. This prevents the use of external configuration memories and contributes towards standardization of integration of CGRAs into RISC-V systems through the use of a custom instruction extension designed for the purpose.

In summary, we explore compilation methods to extract mappable DFGs from both C code and ONNX models, in all cases leveraging the MLIR framework to identify candidate code sections and generate the final binaries for the system. We target our own existing CGRA design [1], which is currently supported by a mapper which consumes DFGs extracted from the analysis of MLIR code.

3.1 MLIR Dialect for DFG Extraction

We now explain the C/C++ input path, which relies on extracting candidate DFGs from textual MLIR representation. We have used Polygeist [13] to generate MLIR from conventional C/C++ code, and a custom dialect which, after detecting and transforming patterns of operations that are available on the CGRA, encapsulates them for the following mapping step.

Figure 2a shows the generated MLIR for C input sources using Polygeist. This is standard MLIR, so polyhedral optimizations can be applied at this stage. Figure 2b shows the use of our dialect for partitioning the computation, where the `cgra.deploy` scope contains the multiply and accumulate operation, which we identify by pattern matching. The respective statements were also converted to the existing `vector` dialect for an easier stream from memory, thus removing the `affine.for` loop after doing a full unroll. We explored the possibility of using MLIR's `--view-op-graph` pass to generate a graph for mapping, but as this graph is overly annotated and not suitably structured for a CGRA mapper,

we are developing a custom pass to refine and clean up the DFG, removing visualization overhead and focusing on CGRA-relevant operations.

Regarding the use of ONNX models as inputs, `onnx-mlir` can generate input code similar to Figure 2a. Therefore, we initially explored this method to arrive at a common intermediate representation early for both C/C++ input and ONNX input, which could be subject to the same transformations and pattern matching. The `onnx-mlir` tool can generate the native `onnx` dialect or the commonly used upstream dialects like `arith` or `affine`. The issue regarding the former is that statements like `onnx.matmul` are too high-level for direct pattern matching into mappable code segments, as they implicitly represent N-dimensional loops containing multiple operations. For the latter, lowering to such dialects expands the implicit operations, but there is total information loss regarding the graph structure of the original ONNX model, including attributes like tensor sizes.

Therefore, to support ONNX models as inputs, we explore how to directly transform ONNX graphs to a DFG format. By making the DFG output from both input paths equivalent, mapping can be carried out directly with both methods in the same way, and any algorithm for spatial methods as described in the literature [12] may be used. The MLIR code that is not deployed on the CGRA is then lowered to a RISC-V binary through LLVM. Once it is executed, the main program will handle the CGRA configuration of the mapped operations and its synchronization with the CGRA with a custom extension.

3.2 Directly Converting ONNX Models to DFGs

The first step of the ONNX path converts models into DFGs by decomposing high-level operations into lower-level operations, which we have implemented in JavaScript/TypeScript. The process is represented in the bottom highlighted portion of Figure 1, and includes parsing the ONNX model, initializing a DFG structure in `Cytoscape.js` [4], a powerful graph manipulation and visualization library. Using this representation, we decompose operations, perform optimizations, and finally generate the DFG. Optionally, Javascript code can be generated, which implements the DFG’s dataflow, allowing for functional validation versus the original model.

ONNX Model Parsing and JSON Conversion ONNX files represent trained AI models as graphs where nodes are high-level operations, such as matrix multiplications or convolutions, where the input and output data sizes can be N-dimensional tensors. However, ONNX files are a binary representation of inference models and thus are not readily suitable for manipulation. We exploit the fact that they are encoded as a Protocol Buffer, whose schema is publicly available, to implement parsing similar to `onnx2json`. While this tool is limited to serialization, our implementation further parses and decomposes high-level operations, translating them into an interactive graph for visualization. The resulting structured data captures the nodes, edges, and attributes of the ONNX model, enabling straightforward manipulation. The JSON format also includes essential metadata for each node, such as the operation type, input-output details,

Fig. 3. ONNX model graph format (Figure 3a) vs initial Cytoscape graph conversion (Figure 3b), as rendered by our conversion tool

and data shapes, laying the foundation for subsequent graph creation. With this JSON object we build the initial Cytoscape graph without losing any information, as it allows for the clear delineation of input, output, and intermediate nodes, which the next stage leverages.

Cytoscape Graph Initialization After parsing, we encapsulate the information in a Cytoscape graph object via a custom wrapper for this library. The graph now directly mimics the representation in the ONNX file and includes: *Input and Output Nodes*, where each corresponds to the model’s inputs and outputs, preserving interface with external data, and is labeled with a variable name, data type, and dimensions; *Operation Nodes*, each representing an ONNX operation (e.g., `Add`, `MatMul`), and containing metadata about connected edges, capturing the logical flow of data through the model; and *Edges*, representing data dependencies, which can exist between any two node types, and with metadata such as placeholders for dimensions and data types, which are resolved later.

Since ONNX graphs do not annotate the tensor size of intermediate edges, we employ a recursive method that finds these dimensions based on the operation type and the input tensors’ dimensions. We start from the operation nodes that connect to the output nodes and check if the tensor dimensions in their input edges are known. If not, we evaluate the operation of the parent nodes generating each input edge. If those dimensions are also unknown, the process is called recursively bottom-to-top until all edges are known. This process always resolves all intermediate edges since the dimensions of the topmost input edges and bottommost output edges are known. At the end of this stage, the graph closely mirrors the source ONNX, but with the explicit dimensions for intermediate values, as shown in Figure 3.

Operation Decomposition After graph initialization, we decompose each high-level operation in the DFG into lower-level arithmetic, logic, and memory operations, providing a finer-grained workload view. We define a library of transformation rules to map complex operations into elementary tasks, producing a DFG where each node represents a fundamental computational unit.

For example, the ONNX `Add` node is decomposed into an element-wise binary addition loop since this node represents the addition of two N-dimensional

Fig. 4. Example conversion outputs after decomposition of ONNX operations for a single ONNX `matmul` node (node order shown left to right)

tensors. The resulting composite node encapsulates this loop, receiving tensors as inputs and iteratively adding corresponding elements. Further optimization passes can bypass the need for a loop for specific tensor sizes, resulting in scalar additions. Figure 4 shows the resulting expanded graph for an input matrix multiplication ONNX node. The implicit nested loops are extracted into a flattened loop, where index counters manage row and column traversal across matrices. Each iteration retrieves matrix elements, multiplies them, and accumulates the result in a designated output tensor position. Once again, specific tensor sizes allow for optimizing away the need for a loop. Other high-level ONNX operations are likewise transformed according to their computational structure. For example, element-wise operations are transformed into single loops, while tensor transformations like `Transpose` could be translated into data reordering tasks.

These transformations ensure that the resulting DFG accurately represents the model’s computation at a lower level of granularity while also being a representation suitable for further analysis and code generation.

DFG Generation and Visualization Finally, after the pipeline is executed, an interactive DFG visualization is rendered, which enables toggling between high and low-level views, examining node attributes, and overall analysis of the conversion results. Through this process, the tool provides a comprehensive transformation and visualization platform for ONNX models, facilitating both analysis and code deployment.

```

function onnxGraph(tensorX, tensorA) {
  let Y = {0: 0, 4: 0, 8: 0, 12: 0, 16: 0, 20: 0, 24: 0, 28: 0, 32: 0};
  for (let Index_0 = 0, i_0 = 0, j_0 = 0, k_0 = 0; Index_0 < 27; Index_0++, k_0++) {
    Y[(j_0 + i_0 * 3) * 4] += tensorX[(i_0 * 3 + k_0) * 4] * tensorA[(k_0 * 3 + j_0) * 4];
    if (k_0 === 2) { k_0 = -1; j_0++; }
    if (j_0 === 3) { j_0 = 0; i_0++; }
  }
  return Y;
}

```

Listing 1: Test code for DFG generated for an input ONNX `matmul` node

4 Ongoing Work

Future work includes improving the partitioning dialect to support loop-level optimizations and improving the identification of off-loadable code in a fully automatic way, including transformations that facilitate pattern matching, all considering the specific parametrization of the target CGRA instance. The subsequent MLIR pass to generate mappable DFGs from the code marked with the partitioning dialect must be fully implemented, and the DFG format from both input paths must be consolidated for consistency and compatibility with a state-of-the-art mapper. The back-end configuration dialect is being defined to facilitate the synchronization with the RISC-V core.

For further ONNX support, ongoing work includes generating the test files and test data. These files are Javascript implementations of the generated DFGs, as exemplified in Listing 1 where the code shown implements the dataflow shown in Figure 3b. By executing both the original model and our generated DFGs equivalent in an ONNX runtime like `onnxruntime-web`, we can check for functional correctness. Other future work includes support for tensor sizes of higher dimensions, the conversion of other types of ONNX input nodes, like convolution and transposition, and refactoring the transformations to maintain ONNX compatible nodes in the DFG throughout the transformation process, only converting to custom nodes suitable for CGRA mapping as late as possible. This allows for the intermediate DFG stages to remain as valid ONNX models for increased flexibility, e.g., execution in `onnxruntime-web`, or for use in other tools like `onnx-mlir`.

5 Conclusion

We have presented the work-in-progress for an integrated flow for RISC-V systems with a CGRA accelerator, supporting inputs from both C/C++ source code and ONNX models. By leveraging the MLIR framework, we intend to generate RISC-V binaries wherein the CGRA interface operations, i.e., configuration and invocation, are embedded. This avoids the need for large configuration memories for the CGRA, reduces integration complexity, and contributes to seamless computation offloading. The latter point is further complimented by the identification or transformation of workload to the CGRA through MLIR compilation, also avoiding the need for explicit use of the CGRA through conventional high-level

APIs, contributing towards the use of CGRA based heterogeneous architectures for edge AI use-cases, without the need for expert knowledge of the underlying hardware.

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